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Report: Understanding and evaluating data discovery and access for restricted data in Canada: A metadata assessment of health data sources

Discovery and Metadata Expert Group

**Digital Research
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The Alliance Data Discovery and Metadata Expert Group (DMEG), initiated the Access-Limited Data Discovery Working Group (WG) in 2021. The WG conducted an evaluation to assess the discovery and access conditions of currently available restricted and access-limited research data in Canada.

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Abstract

This project identified Canadian restricted and access-limited data sources (n=137) and evaluated a sub-sample (n=48) of restricted health data sources to measure how discoverable and accessible the datasets are to potential researchers. To identify common elements used by the data sources, we inventoried and mapped elements to existing metadata standards for discovery and access. Overall, for many data sources, there was incomplete information and only basic metadata provided about datasets. Across the sub-sample, none of the data sources had implemented any metadata standards for sharing information about restricted data, which poses significant barriers for the discovery and reuse of restricted health data in Canada.

Based on these findings, stakeholders across the research data ecosystem should consider establishing key recommendations and set priorities for collaborators to improve restricted data discovery and access systems and policies in Canada. These key recommendations are included within this report, alongside a description of the project.

Background

Over the past decade, Canada has made significant strides towards fostering a more open scientific research community, including promoting open government and open science practices, policies, and supporting investments into national digital research infrastructure and services.¹ Improving the discovery of and access to Canadian research data highlights the need for greater collaboration across the larger open data discovery and research ecosystem, where it is envisioned all research data can be discoverable especially for data that is made available under restricted or controlled access conditions.

There are many challenges associated with the discovery of restricted-data including the availability of metadata for describing data and access information, such as request access procedures and data use licences or agreements. Open metadata for discovery supports data findability, data descriptions and standards, data linkages and citations for reuse of and collaboration across funders, institutions, disciplinary communities and scholarly research, aiming to facilitate open and interdisciplinary data reuse across all research communities.

Project Overview

In light of these challenges, the Digital Research Alliance of Canada's Discovery & Metadata Expert Group (DMEG) initiated the Access-Limited Data Discovery Working Group (WG) in 2021 to assess the current restricted data discovery and access landscape in Canada.² We undertook this project to identify and evaluate the discovery and access characteristics of Canadian restricted data sources, defined here as data that are not immediately accessible

¹ Digital Research Alliance of Canada (2022). Alliance RDM Strategy, Accessed June 20, 2024. https://alliancecan.ca/sites/default/files/2024-02/rdm_strategy_2022-09.pdf

² Digital Research Alliance of Canada. (n.d.). Network of Experts. Accessed March 25, 2024. <https://alliancecan.ca/en/services/research-data-management/network-experts>

because they are restricted due to some commercial, ethical, or legal reasons, or they are only available upon request and require additional access controls that must be established and adhered to in order to access them.

This project resulted in two separate studies that were published in 2024.^{3, 4} Additional datasets and documentation are available on the WG's Open Science Framework project space.⁵ We recommend reviewing these resources for complete details of our methodology and results.

In this report, we provide a brief summary of the project's findings and include further analysis and recommendations for consideration by the larger open science and RDM community in Canada.

Part 1: Canadian Health Data Sources Identification & Evaluation

From January 2021 to November 2021, the first part of our project focused on identifying as many Canadian restricted data sources as possible (n=137) and then evaluating characteristics related to discovery and access in a subset of Canadian health data sources (n=48/137) using a [grading rubric](#) designed by the WG. The rubric, inspired by the FAIR Principles, considers a set of discovery and access conditions and requirements related to data discovery and access with scoring grades of A through C for each.⁶ Our results highlight areas for improvement for restricted health data discovery and access in Canada in three broad areas:

- ▶ **Open Discovery:** Many data sources did not make data discoverable using best practices or open metadata. The vast majority of data sources received low data discovery grades due to a lack of any metadata standards or availability of metadata (10/48, **21% received a high grade**).
- ▶ **Data Description and Documentation:** Most sources provided at least some descriptive information about the dataset including its scope, purpose, and nature of collection (30/48, **62.5% received an A or B grade**), however relatively fewer sources shared any dataset documentation, such as variable information or codebooks (21/48, **43.8% received an A or B grade**).

³ Read, K. B., Gibson, G. A., Leahey, A., Peterson, L., Rutley, S., Shi, J., Smith, V., & Stathis, K. 2024. Understanding the challenges associated with finding and accessing restricted data in Canada: a mixed methods study. *FACETS*. 9: 1-9. <https://doi.org/10.1139/facets-2023-0102>

⁴ Read, K.B., Gibson, G., Leahey, A., Peterson, L., Rutley, S., Shi, J., Smith, V., & Stathis, K. (2024, 8 16). Identifying metadata commonalities across restricted health data sources: A mixed methods study exploring how to improve the discovery of and access to restricted datasets. *Journal of eScience Librarianship* 13(2) :e907. <https://doi.org/10.7191/jeslib.907>

⁵ Read, K. B., Gibson, G. A., Leahey, A., Peterson, L., Rutley, S., Shi, J., Smith, V., & Stathis, K. (2022, August 18). Identifying and evaluating restricted data sources in Canada: Recommendations for improving data discovery and access. Retrieved from osf.io/5nh2s

⁶ Read, K. B., Gibson, G. A., Leahey, A., Peterson, L., Rutley, S., Smith, V., & Stathis, K. (2022, July 13). Access-Limited Data Source Grading Rubric. <https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/KC4U9>

- ▶ **Data Access:** Most sources provided at least some information about restricted data access procedures (33/48, **68.8% received an A or B grade**), however most were assigned low overall data accessibility scores due to a lack of comprehensive data access information, such as transparent pricing details and eligibility criteria to access.

Part 2: Identifying Metadata Commonalities Within Data Sources

Using our sample of health data sources in Part 1 (n=48), from December 2021 to March 2023, we reviewed and compiled metadata from each source and identified metadata commonalities across them. These metadata commonalities were then grouped into common themes and mapped to existing metadata standards to assess how well they align with them.

After organising metadata commonalities by theme, we identified 35 common dataset metadata elements and 27 common metadata access elements. Refer to the publication for the complete list of common elements.⁷

Metadata Mapping Comparison

The common dataset and access elements identified were then mapped to five data-specific metadata schemas to understand how well current metadata standards support discovery and access for restricted datasets: [DataCite \(version 4.4\)](#), [DDI-Lifecycle \(version 3.1\)](#), [DDI-Codebook \(version 2.5\)](#), [DCAT Vocabulary \(version 3\)](#), and [DATS \(version 2.2\)](#).

Elements in each schema were evaluated on an exact, partial, or no match scale to determine their alignment with the found common elements.

Discovery Metadata Alignment

The DDI-Lifecycle schema mapped most closely to the metadata elements extracted from the data sources, however this schema may not be as widely adopted compared to others such as DataCite, which returned fewer exact and partial matches. Regardless of the metadata schemas, none of the sources had standard metadata support or mentioned these metadata standards.

Access Metadata Alignment

No access metadata from existing schemas was found to map clearly with our common elements. Although all five schemas include some access metadata, their broad scope does not support the granularity and complexity required to describe access restrictions and request processes for restricted data. The variability of request procedures across data sources further complicates standardisation.

⁷ Read, K.B., Gibson, G., Leahey, A., Peterson, L., Rutley, S., Shi, J., Smith, V., & Stathis, K. (2024, 8 16). Identifying metadata commonalities across restricted health data sources: A mixed methods study exploring how to improve the discovery of and access to restricted datasets. *Journal of eScience Librarianship* 13(2) :e907. <https://doi.org/10.7191/jeslib.907>

Restricted Data Sources and Next Steps

The results of this project indicate a clear need for standardised metadata and infrastructure for restricted data providers to make their data more discoverable and accessible to align with funder and journal policies, such as the Tri-Agency RDM Policy.⁸ Further understanding and development around shared data practices, metadata standards, and more support for the open discoverability and access to restricted or controlled access data. Activities to improve the discovery and access of restricted data can be undertaken by many stakeholders across the digital research ecosystem, including funders, scholarly publishers, institutions, infrastructure providers, and researchers.

Key Recommendations

For stakeholders across the RDM and data discovery ecosystem:

- ▶ Adopt or adapt existing metadata standards such as the general purpose [DataCite Metadata Schema](#) and disciplinary-specific [DDI Codebook and Lifecycle](#), where possible and appropriate to help support discovery of research data, including restricted access data.
- ▶ Invest in consensus building and development of new or extended metadata standards to enhance data discovery and sharing of access details for restricted and controlled access data, including where possible metadata and documentation pertaining to variables available in a dataset(s).
- ▶ Develop common language for terms of use, licenses, agreements, etc. and guidance across restricted data access programs and services to reduce the burden for researchers applying for access and custodians and stewards providing access.
 - This may include access request procedures, policies, data sharing agreements, licensing templates, and data access mechanisms.
- ▶ Investigate and encourage the adoption of persistent Identifiers for restricted data (e.g. DataCite DOIs to assign metadata for restricted data and make them publicly searchable and usable by aggregators and tools such as Lunaris).
- ▶ In some cases, access can be facilitated by already established frameworks and services, where possible or otherwise similar initiatives should be evaluated for invested development, such as for research access to administrative, hospital, and government health data sources across provinces in Canada (e.g. DASH initiative) and for Statistics Canada master microdata files administered by the Canadian Research Data Centre Network (CRDCN) and public use microdata files through the Data Liberation Initiative (DLI).

⁸ Government of Canada (2021, March 14). Tri-Agency Research Data Management Policy. <https://science.gc.ca/site/science/en/interagency-research-funding/policies-and-guidelines/research-data-management/tri-agency-research-data-management-policy>

- ▶ Develop guidance on long-term stewardship considerations for access to restricted data to enable reproducibility or limit data loss, given the finite project timelines and resources afforded to most researchers and data lifecycles.
- ▶ Engage in further dialogue and commitments to build capacity, infrastructure, training and service provision to enable stewardship of Canadian restricted data and research data. This should include outreach and collaboration across sectors, including industry, academia, government, and non-profit organisations.

For the Digital Research Alliance of Canada:

- ▶ Engage with restricted data providers, institutions and data managers to further understand the barriers and pathways forward for improving the discovery and access of restricted and controlled access research data.
- ▶ Begin incorporating restricted data sources identified in this study in national data discovery platforms, such as [Lunaris](#), to improve the discovery and potential reuse of restricted research data (where appropriate).
- ▶ Apply similar approaches demonstrated in this study to evaluate the metadata needs for restricted and sensitive research data in Canada as part of ongoing service development and new initiatives including the [Controlled Access Management \(CAM\) Project](#), a collaborative project to develop a roadmap to pilot technical and policy solutions for secure storage, sharing, and reuse of restricted data in Canada.

For the Digital Research Alliance of Canada, Canada's Tri-Agencies, other funding bodies, and other government bodies:

In particular, Innovation Science and Economic Development Canada and the Office of the Chief Science Advisor:

- ▶ Support the development of standardised workflows to enhance discovery and access to restricted research data. This should include a range of adaptable infrastructure options for Canadian researchers, institutions, and data stewards for the management of legal and ethical sharing and reuse of restricted data that respects jurisdictional boundaries and workflows, processes, and sharing policies.
- ▶ Offer funding opportunities to support the development and adoption of data discovery and access standards in research data repositories and infrastructure, including security, enhanced privacy and protection of data, open metadata sharing, and metadata standards.
- ▶ Offer funding opportunities to support further research examining and addressing gaps in research data policies and related technical requirements for the ongoing and future needs related to storage, discovery, management, and access to restricted research data in Canada.
- ▶ Develop training programs for restricted data stewards and custodians to develop data documentation and reusable frameworks for maximising the potential of secondary reuse of restricted data when appropriate.

- ▶ Facilitate a community of practice consisting of restricted data curators, stewards, and custodians to support the adoption of the standards and workflows listed above.
- ▶ Expand and offer funding for curation and management of restricted data focusing on supporting metadata and documentation for restricted data.
- ▶ Develop guidance for managing and providing access to restricted data in light of Tri-Agency policies.

For librarians and national repositories:

- ▶ Train researchers who collect restricted data on how best to make it discoverable, accessible, and re-usable.
- ▶ Encourage researchers to connect early with their Research Ethics Board to ensure participant consent and ethics approval reflect plans for data discovery, accessibility, and re-usability.
- ▶ Raise awareness of the value and importance of making restricted data discoverable and accessible to their research communities.
- ▶ Advocate to national bodies, including the aforementioned organisations, to develop infrastructure to support restricted data.
- ▶ Share challenges and experiences of researchers looking to improve the discovery of their restricted datasets with these national bodies.
- ▶ Encourage the use of minimum standards for open discovery of research data, including open metadata and information about restricted data and access procedures.
- ▶ Encourage data descriptions and open documentation as essential for understanding and discovery and reuse of research data.
- ▶ Develop documentation and provide institutional services and guidance to researchers and data managers across institutions.

Conclusion

This project evaluated how well 48 Canadian restricted health data sources made their datasets discoverable and accessible to potential researchers, and extracted information and metadata for the datasets including the descriptions, access restrictions, and request procedures to identify common metadata elements across data sources. The potential for discovery and reuse of restricted health data in Canada is limited by the lack of metadata available about the datasets and how to access them, the inability for current infrastructure to support restricted data, the lack of guidance for data stewards to adopt data discovery best practices, and a lack of clarity from funders on how restricted data should be made discoverable and accessible in compliance with data management policies.

We strongly recommend that the various stakeholders highlighted in this report establish priorities around restricted data and collaborate to improve its discovery in Canada. Ongoing engagement with stakeholders is crucial to ensure that developments continue to respond to the needs and concerns of the community. Without metadata, infrastructure, and education for stewards of restricted data in Canada, the majority of this valuable research data will remain hidden and inaccessible.

Relevant Project Resources

- Digital Research Alliance of Canada. (n.d.). Network of Experts. Accessed March 25, 2024. <https://alliancecan.ca/en/services/research-data-management/network-experts>
- Read, K. B., Gibson, G. A., Leahey, A., Peterson, L., Rutley, S., Smith, V., & Stathis, K. (2022, July 13). Access-Limited Data Source Grading Rubric. <https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/KC4U9>
- Read, K. B., Gibson, G. A., Leahey, A., Peterson, L., Rutley, S., Smith, V., Stathis, K., & Shi, J. (2022, August 9). Canadian data source identification and evaluation datasets. <https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/UBZN2>
- Read, K. B., Gibson, G. A., Leahey, A., Peterson, L., Rutley, S., Shi, J., Smith, V., & Stathis, K. (2024, January 19). Datasets Exploring Metadata Commonalities Across Restricted Health Data Sources in Canada. <https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/TXRVE>
- Read, K. B., Gibson, G. A., Leahey, A., Peterson, L., Rutley, S., Shi, J., Smith, V., & Stathis, K. (2024). Understanding the challenges associated with finding and accessing restricted data in Canada: a mixed methods study. *FACETS*. 9: 1-9. <https://doi.org/10.1139/facets-2023-0102>
- Read, K.B., Gibson, G, Leahey, A, Peterson, L, Rutley, S, Shi, J, Smith, V, & Stathis, K. (2024, 8 16). Identifying metadata commonalities across restricted health data sources: A mixed methods study exploring how to improve the discovery of and access to restricted datasets. *Journal of eScience Librarianship* 13(2) :e907. <https://doi.org/10.7191/jeslib.907>